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VERTICAL DRIFT CHIMNEYS, DIGITISATION, CRPS

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Abstract:

Task 9.3 foresees the study of a novel charge readout scheme for very large time projection chambers named Vertical Drift. This technology avoids using wires to collect the signals of the electrons, originating from charged particles' ionization, at the end of their drift path. This kind of development program, included in task 9.3, is unprecedented and innovative in the domain of LAr Time Projection Chambers (TPC). In Vertical Drift the wire planes are replaced by stacks of perforated printed circuit boards integrated in Charge Readout Planes (CRP) with an area of $3 \times 3.3 \text{ m}^2$, covering the surface at the top and bottom of the detector. This active surface receives the electrons drifting thanks to a uniform electric field aligned along the vertical axis. Task 9.3 focuses on the readout of the top-drift volume of the detector. The cryogenic ASIC amplifiers used to read the signals are integrated in this layout in front-end cards hosted in cryostat penetrations "signal feedthrough chimneys" which make them accessible from outside during detector operation. The digitization electronics on the detector roof is cabled to warm-flanges closing the top part of the chimneys. This technology, which is foreseen to equip a DUNE Far Detector module, underwent extensive large-scale tests at the CERN Neutrino Platform in 2021-2022. These tests successfully demonstrated its validity. During 2024 all

these technologies reached development maturity ready for production and passed the DUNE Production Readiness Reviews. This deliverable document reports about the overall work and developments performed on the CRP readout system for the DUNE Vertical Drift Far Detector module which is currently in construction.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2025

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Executive summary

Task 9.3 deals with the developments associated to the demonstration of the Vertical Drift (VD) charge readout technology which is a novel design of LAr TPC detectors, based on the use of perforated printed circuit boards instead of wire planes for the readout of the ionization signals in LAr Time Projection Chambers (TPC).

The Vertical Drift design is particularly suited to build and instrument very large LAr detectors in a simpler and cost-effective way. VD, at the time of this deliverable report, is now being deployed as the first DUNE Far Detector module (FD-VD). Task 9.3 focused on the demonstration of the configuration for the readout of the top-drift volume of FD-VD by developing an optimized configuration for the Charge Readout Planes (CRP) and their associated electronics. The Charge Readout Planes host the perforated printed circuit boards anode planes and are used in order to collect the ionization signals from the TPC drift volume and to provide a 3 independent views imaging of the tracks left by charged particles in liquid argon. This charge is then amplified by cryogenic ASIC amplifiers hosted in the chimneys and then digitized by microTCA electronics on the cryostat roof.

This deliverable report includes the overall results from an intensive prototyping campaign on the Vertical Drift technology, which was conducted in 2021-2022 by using the infrastructure provided by the CERN Neutrino Platform including a dedicated Cold-Box cryostat of the exact size of a VD Charge Readout Plane unit. This campaign included the successful development and tests of the first two CRP units corresponding to the final layout foreseen for the top drift volume of FD-VD and of their associated electronics and signal feedthrough chimneys.

1. INTRODUCTION

Task 9.3 Vertical Drift (VD) Charge Readout is a detector development oriented to the construction of the DUNE LAr Far Detector module (FD-VD). Vertical Drift is a completely innovative technique that allows reading the ionization of charged tracks in LAr Time Projection Chambers without instrumenting the anode surface with wire planes instead exploiting Charge Readout Plane (CRP) units (each one covering $3 \times 3.3 \text{ m}^2$ active surface) made of two layers of perforated anode Printed Circuit Boards (PCB). The anode-perforated PCBs' copper layers are segmented in strips of about 5 mm pitch in order to define readout views. The two PCB layers provide two views (at ± 30 degrees (with respect to the beam direction in FD-VD) reading induction signals and a last view at 90 degrees collecting the electrons. The Vertical Drift layout and the use of perforated anodes instead of wire planes make the construction and installation of very large size detectors cheap and effective.

The anode planes are coupled to dedicated cryogenic Front-End (FE) and digitization warm electronics (altogether defined as: Top Drift Electronics, TDE) explicitly developed and optimized for this configuration present in the upper part of the drift volume of the DUNE FD-VD detector module. Special mechanical cryostat penetrations "Chimneys" host the FE boards with cryogenic amplifiers, preserving their accessibility at any time without interfering with the detector operation. Vertical Drift is an evolution and further simplification of the Dual-Phase technique already

developed in AIDA2020. Both the Dual-Phase and Vertical Drift developments have been strongly supported by the CERN Neutrino Platform infrastructure located in the EHN1 hall.

The demonstration at large scale of this unprecedented detector technology corresponding to the Vertical Drift for the DUNE top drift volume of FD-VD has been the goal of task 9.3 and it represented an essential step before moving to the construction of the DUNE FD-VD. In the years 2021 and 2022, CRP planes with perforated anodes were constructed and tested, together with the associated readout electronics and chimneys, at the CERN Neutrino Platform with a dedicated cold-box cryostat, capable of hosting a complete VD CRP and of operating the CRP in LAr TPC configuration, collecting cosmic rays tracks for its accurate characterization.

The campaign at the CERN Neutrino Platform started with the test of the first Vertical Drift CRP (CRP1), in the fall of 2021. CRP1 was shared in two equal halves among the top-drift and bottom-drift configurations. This first test included two consecutive cold-box runs. CRP1 was tested again, in a version CRP1b including some improvements of the grounding for the bottom-drift readout half, in May-June 2022 with a new cold-box test.

Crucial tests of the first two complete versions (CRP2 and CRP3) of Vertical Drift CRPs in their final strip layout configuration foreseen for DUNE FD-VD were performed in 2022. These tests were successfully accomplished between July and November 2022, providing excellent results which validated the CRP design. All these cold-box tests were based on the same readout configuration of the Top Drift Electronics, which included the front-end analog cards hosting the ASIC amplifiers and the microTCA digitization electronics. All these elements represent innovative developments performed by the Top Drift Electronics Consortium.

The top drift CRPs and the associated electronics were then successfully integrated in the NP02 cryostat containing a vertical slice of the FD-VD module in 2023. This deliverable reports about the readout electronics developments occurred since 2021 and on their integration in the overall goal pursued by task 9.3 of demonstrating the Vertical Drift technology.

2. ACTIVITIES AND RESULTS

2.1. VERTICAL DRIFT COLD-BOX TESTS AND TOP DRIFT ELECTRONICS DEVELOPMENTS

Vertical Drift Charge Readout Planes (CRPs) with perforated anodes, designed to be the modular anode readout unit for the FD-VD detector, were constructed and tested, together with their readout electronics, at the CERN Neutrino Platform with a dedicated Cold-Box (CB) cryostat.

The year 2021 saw a very intensive test program at the CERN Neutrino Platform in the EHN1 hall, where a new Cold-Box (CB) cryostat was built and equipped, for the tests of the Vertical Drift CRPs [1] in proximity of the NP02 cryostat, to share the same cryogenics system.

The Cold-Box size was precisely tailored to contain and operate a single CRP module. The CB can be operated in Time Projection Chamber configuration with 30 cm vertical drift space, present in between the CRP lower surface and the cathode plane. This drift distance allows collecting very large samples (order of millions) of cosmic ray tracks that can be exploited and analyzed in order to fully characterize the CRP response and its associated electronics, both items covered by task 9.3.

The CRP is suspended from the roof of the Cold-Box (Figure 1). The CB roof can be inserted and extracted from the top in the Cold-Box cryostat. The CB roof is used at the same time to seal the cryostat and to support the CRP. Once the roof is sealed, the top CRP constitutes the anode of the TPC detector. This configuration features a drift length corresponding to the distance from the anode down to the cathode plane element lying on the floor of the CB cryostat (Figure 2).

Fig. 1: A Vertical Drift top-drift Charge Readout Plane (CRP2) suspended from the Cold-Box roof while being transported to the Cold-Box location. The bottom copper surface of the first layer of perforated anodes PCBs is visible from below. At the sides one can see the flat cables bringing signals from the anodes to the chimneys which are hosting the cryogenic readout amplifiers

In order to first test and qualify the CRP at warm (room temperature) before operating them in TPC mode, a complementary setup to the Cold-box (the Faraday Cage) was also developed and built in 2022. This facility was exploited for systematic CRP tests at warm. It allowed for full access to the CRP during the preliminary tests needed to optimize the CRP electrical configuration and to check all connections.

Fig. 2: Cold-Box cryostat built for the tests of the Vertical Drift Charge Readout Planes in TPC mode. This picture shows at its top the cold-box roof with the CRP suspended below while being lowered to close the cold-box cryostat (at the bottom of the picture) with a cathode module laying on its floor

The Faraday cage (Figure 3) is closed at its top by the Cold-Box roof, which has the CRP suspended below. This configuration allows performing for each CRP a first test at warm in the Faraday Cage and then moving the roof with the CRP suspended below to the Cold-Box for its test in liquid argon in TPC mode. The Faraday cage completely shields the CRP and its strips from picking up EMI noise from the external environment, in the same way as the Cold-Box. At the same time, the Faraday cage is designed to allow for complete access for people and to provide working space around the CRP during the warm tests.

In 2022 all CRP tests (CRP1b, CRP2, CRP3) were systematically conducted in two steps: with a first operation at warm in the Faraday cage in order to cross-check the noise levels and the electrical connections and then with extensive operation and data collection with cosmic rays in the Cold-Box filled with LAr and operated in TPC mode.

Fig. 3: CRP2 while being tested at warm in the Faraday cage setup before undergoing a Cold-Box test. The CRP is suspended from the Cold-Box roof which closes the top side of the Faraday Cage. The same roof is then used to seal the Cold-Box cryostat during the tests in TPC mode. The Cold-Box roof is fully instrumented with the analog readout electronics in the chimneys and the uTCA digitization system.

2.2. READOUT ELEMENTS AND RESULTS

The analog cryogenic amplifiers are hosted at the bottom of the chimneys (Figure 4). The chimneys are stainless steel pipes going through the insulation of the roof of the cryostat until reaching a height, inside the cryostat gas ullage, which is close to the CRP. The bottom of each chimney is sealed by a cold-flange PCB (Fig. 4) which isolates the chimney internal volume and prevents from contaminating the ultra-pure LAr environment of the cryostat during access to the FE electronics or the chimney operation.

The FE cards with the cryogenic amplifiers (Figure 5), mounted on long blades sliding inside the chimney, can be plugged to the connectors located on the top side of the cold-flange PCB in order to receive the signals from the TPC. The bottom face of the cold-flange PCB hosts the connectors which are used to plug flat cables bringing the signals from the CRP induction or charge collection views.

The FE cards operate at a temperature of about 110 K, which is naturally present in the cryostat ullage space just above the LAr level, being LAr at 87 K. The chimney is sealed at its top with a vertical warm-flange which is instrumented with the connectors needed for the cable bringing the amplified signals to the digitization electronics contained in uTCA crates on the cryostat roof and the connectors needed to distribute power to the FE cards. The chimney is filled with N₂ in order to avoid humidity condensation on the FE cards during operation at cold. Five chimneys, containing up to 10 FE cards each, were integrated on the Cold-Box roof in order to allow for the tests of each top-drift charge readout plane.

Both the FE cards and the microTCA digitization boards (AMC) have identical channel granularity, corresponding to 64 channels per board, which are interconnected 1:1 on the readout chain. Each

uTCA crate is hosting up to 10 AMC boards. The AMC boards (Figure 6) exploit commercial ADC chips (AD9257) in order to sample the analog signals at 2.5 MHz. On each AMC board the readout of the ADCs is operated by an FPGA (Cyclone V) running a virtual NIOS II processor.

The FPGA collects the data from the ADCs and then formats the data in UDP packets (jumbo frames) in order to transmit them on the ethernet network to the DAQ backend. Each AMC board features 10 Gbit/s ethernet connectivity to the backplane of the uTCA crate. The synchronization of the sampling on different AMC boards and the tagging on the TAI time for each ADC sample with \sim ns accuracy is ensured by a dedicated White-Rabbit board (WR-MCH), present in each uTCA crate. The WR-MCH exploits dedicated signal lanes present on the crate backplane to deliver with point-to-point connections the timing and clock signals to each AMC. This timing distribution system has been also an innovative development of the top-drift electronics supported within task 9.3.

Each uTCA crate includes a MicroTCA Carrier Hub (MCH) board. The MCH acts as crate controller and it contains as well an ethernet switch connected via the backplane to the single AMC boards. The MCH is capable of handling a total bandwidth of 120 Gbit/s with an external connectivity (corresponding to 12 AMC with 10 Gbit/s bandwidth per AMC) organized in three uplink ports of 40 Gbit/s each.

For the DUNE application, an MCH having a connectivity via a single 40 Gbit/s port was exploited for the acquired data flow to the DAQ back-end. Given the sampling frequency and data format of the DUNE AMCs, with 12 AMC present in the crate the 40Gbit/s uplink of the MCH has about 50% constant bandwidth occupancy.

The system used for the Cold-Box tests represented the very first large-scale application of a uTCA system with 40 Gbit/s connectivity in the HEP community. This application required the implementation of a readout system with 200 Gbit/s total bandwidth.

In 2024, within the scope of a value engineering development, an MCH model with 25 Gbit/s uplink connectivity was also tested and validated. These tests converged to the final configuration which will be used in DUNE. 25 Gbit/s uplink connectivity is exactly tailored to the bandwidth produced by the 12 DUNE AMC boards present in each crate. This solution allows performing scaling economies in the design of the DUNE ethernet network because the most diffused 100Gbit/s industry standard, used at the level of the switches and network interface cards of the DAQ system, is a multiple of 25Gbit/s.

Fig. 4: (Left) Sketch of a signal feedthrough chimney hosting the FE cards with the cryogenic amplifiers. The chimney goes through the cryostat insulation (closed view). The open view shows a section of the chimney pipe which allows seeing the blade with the FE card plugged on the cold flange. (Right) view of the top of the system with the uTCA crates for the current implementation in the Cold-Box tests for the Vertical Drift.

Fig. 5: Picture of a Top-Drift Electronics analog Front-End (FE) board which supports four cryogenic ASIC amplifiers with 16 channels each (64 readout channels per board)

Fig. 6: Picture of a uTCA Top-Drift Electronics AMC digitization board

The first CRP prototype (CRP1) was successfully tested in November-December 2021. This CRP was instrumented shared in common for the top-drift readout, on which task 9.3 is focused, (TDE) and the bottom-drift (BDE) readout. TDE and BDE were both developed since 2021 for the DUNE Vertical Drift Far Detector module.

CRP1 was re-tested in the Faraday cage and in the cold-box in May-June 2022 (CRP1b) after having implemented some grounding improvements needed by the BDE readout. This test was also the occasion to check the stability of the response after a long-time span and after several mechanical manipulations had occurred to the CRP.

Following the tests on CRP1, and physics optimization studies based on simulations of the reconstruction of neutrino events in FD-VD, the CRP anode channels layout and strip orientation (3 views at 90° , $+30^\circ$ and -30° with respect to the beam) (Fig.7) were finalized in a common geometry to be exploited for both top-drift and bottom-drift CRPs.

This configuration was primarily implemented and tested in 2022 on CRP2 and on CRP3. CRP2 and CRP3 were the first Vertical Drift readout units with the final FD-VD layout. They were both top-drift CRPs. The channels counting for the final design of a top-drift CRP readout amounts to 48 FE cards (hosted in the CB tests in 5 chimneys) and 48 AMC digitization cards (hosted in 5 uTCA crates) per CRP, for a total of 3072 charge readout channels.

The first full-size top-drift CRP (CRP2) was constructed and tested in July 2022 during the continuation of the Cold-Box tests campaign foreseen in 2022 (Fig.8). A second first full-size top-drift CRP (CRP3), with the same anode layout of CRP2, was also fully tested in October 2022.

The first perforated PCB, which is facing the drift volume, has only its top copper layer read out with strips, constituting an induction view (Induction_1). A bipolar signal is induced on the Induction_1 view by the electrons while they are approaching the CRP from the TPC drift volume, passing through the holes of the first perforated PCB (2.4 mm diameter) and eventually getting away from the top face of the PCB.

The electrons then continue their path through the gap in between the two PCBs of the anode stack and they pass through the holes of the second perforated PCB (see Fig. 7). The electrons induce therefore an induction signal on the bottom layer of the second PCB (Induction_2). This layer is segmented in strips with a complementary orientation than the one of Induction 2.

Eventually the electrons, exiting from the holes of the second PCB, are collected by the strips implemented on its top copper layer (Collection View), yet with a different orientation.

The PCB copper layers are biased at progressively higher voltages (see Fig. 7). This biasing is needed in order to make the induction views transparent to the flow of the electrons through the PCB holes with no electrons captured on their copper layers during their movement through the PCB holes. The electrons are eventually collected only by the strips of the last view present on the top face of the second PCB and not by the previous layers, which are seeing only electrical bipolar signals induced by the motion of the electrons. The charge integral of these bipolar signals is zero.

The signals collected by the strips belonging to the different readout views are routed at the sides of the PCBs by edge-cards. The edge-cards, plugged perpendicularly to the CRP PCBs, bring the electrical signals to adapter boards installed on top of the CRP. The adapter boards host the connectors needed for the flat cables which will eventually bring these signals to the chimneys. The edge-cards provide the routing of the electrical signals from the strips to the flat cables, while at the same time introducing very little dead areas on the CRP sides.

The stack of the two perforated PCBs is integrated and mechanically supported by a composite FR4 structure frame. A CRP, in order to ease its transportation and installation, is divided in two halves (CRU) which can be assembled together after transportation in the final CRP (see Fig.11). The perforated PCB panels have the size of a CRU (3336 mm x 1444 mm) and are each one assembled by gluing together 6 sub-panels of smaller dimensions (see Fig. 9). After gluing, the electrical continuity of the strips across different sub-panels is ensured by implementing silver printed joints. Details of the CRP structures with pictures taken during the CRP assembly process are shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 9: Assembly from sub-panels of a perforated PCB panel corresponding to a CRP half

Fig. 10: (Top) Structural details of the perforated PCB panels. (Bottom) CRP assembly including the composite frame support structure and a stack of two layers of perforated PCBs with the edge-cards (pictures taken during the CRP assembly activities)

Fig. 11: Assembly of the two halves (CRUs) composing CRP3 and final view of CRP3 fully assembled. The composite structure of CRP3 corresponds to an optimized version, lighter than the first one implemented on CRP2

The top-drift CRP design and construction process demonstrated to completely fulfil the planarity specifications needed to guarantee the uniformity of the drift electric field and uniform collection of the charges over the CRP surface. In 2022 the Cold-Box tests of the final VD CRP layout demonstrated the good performance of the CRP and of its associated electronics, including the operation of the exploited chimneys. The results were completely fulfilling expectations.

A very large statistics sample of cosmic ray tracks was collected to characterize the stable operation of the detector and the uniformity in the response of the CRP. A typical event containing cosmic ray tracks is shown in Fig. 12. The track at the left shows also a delta-ray electron visible along the trajectory of the muon.

Fig. 12: Example of clean cosmic ray tracks collected during the operation of CRP2 in the Cold-Box

This test program fully demonstrated the readout of the top-drift volume of FD-VD. The two final top-drift CRPs (CRP2 and CRP3) were then integrated in 2023 inside the already existing NP02 cryostat (ProtoDUNE-VD) in order to mimic a vertical slide of FD-VD (see Fig.13).

Given the dimensions of the already existing NP02 cryostat, this slice has, for both the top and bottom drift volumes, half of the drift length (3m) than in the FD-VD detector. The 6m drift space and the associated HV system to distribute 300kV at the cathode had been already demonstrated in 2022 in the NP02 cryostat by using the dual-phase CRPs and the TDE electronics.

Fig. 13: The NP02 cryostat hosting the integration of a vertical slice of FD-VD

This FD-VD “Module-0” integration test allowed for a global and complete integration exercise of different VD elements previously independently validated (top and bottom CRPs, cathode modules and photon detectors) and to then cross-check the underground installation procedures for FD-VD.

Cold-Box runs repeated at large distance in time on the same CRP, after several thermal cycles and manipulation on the CRP structures had happened, demonstrated the robustness of the CRPs and of its readout system, as well as the reproducibility of the detector operation and of the results obtained.

This aspect is shown in Figure 14, where the dE/dx distribution measured on CRP1/CRP1b with large samples of cosmic ray tracks is compared among the runs taken in November 2021 and in June 2022. The two Landau distributions in black and red, measured at different epochs, are perfectly overlaying.

Fig. 14: Stability in the dE/dx response of CRP1 assessed by comparing two different cold-box runs CRP1/CRP1b

The noise performance of the readout system is shown in Figure 15. The noise levels were found to be equivalent to the ones of ProtoDUNE Single-Phase/Horizontal-Drift and matching expectations.

Fig. 15: Noise levels for all readout channels recorded during the cold-box runs of CRP2 and CRP3

The response uniformity of the channels was checked with a dedicated in-situ calibration system capable of performing charge injection with 1% accuracy individually to each readout channel present in the ASIC amplifiers.

As shown in Figure 16, without applying any correction, the response uniformity over all the CRP channels is at the level of 2.5%, while the average response, considering all channels, between the different runs is well within 1%.

Fig. 16: Spread of measured calibration constants for all readout channels during the 3 CRP cold-box runs

After the conclusion of the Cold-Box tests, in 2023, the entire TDE system deployed to read out the two top-drift CRPs (CRP3 and CRP2), which had been previously tested in the Cold-Box, was installed and recommissioned on the roof of the NP02 cryostat, for the integration of the Vertical-Drift Module-0.

A synoptic sketch of the implementation of the Top-Drift electronics Elements for the readout of the DUNE Far detector module VD-FD is represented in Figure 17.

In VD-FD the chimneys are of larger size. They may contain up to 48 front-end cards which are then connected to four uTCA crates. The readout electronics elements represented in the sketch are the same as the ones validated during the CRP Cold-Box tests performed at CERN in 2022.

The chimneys for FD-VD are based on the same design and principles as the ones exploited and validated during the Cold-Box tests and in NP02. The FD-VD chimneys represent an extension of this original design: being of larger diameter they can simply host a larger number of FE cards. Instead of the 10 FE cards as in the Cold-Box or in NP02, the FD-VD chimneys can host 24 or 48 FE cards.

Fig. 17: Summary sketch of the implementation of the Top-Drift Electronics elements for the readout of a large (48 cards) chimney of the DUNE FD-VD far detector module

2.1. DESIGN AND PROTOTYPING OF OPTIMIZED LARGE DIAMETER CHIMNEYS FOR FD-VD

Given the final CRP strips layout corresponding to 48 FE cards and the experience accumulated with the Cold-Box, the chimney design was further developed and optimized in 2022 for FD-VD in order to contain all the 48 cards needed to read out a CRP module.

Chimneys of this size are too large to be implemented in the Cold-Box roof. They are however an evolution of the 10 cards chimneys already exploited for the Cold-Box tests, inheriting from their design. Their development then followed a parallel path to the Cold-Box tests. The design is based on the same concepts already exploited for the cold-flange, the warm flanges and the blades. The larger chimneys are meant to optimize the costs and to reduce the number of penetrations to be implemented on the FD-VD cryostat roof.

Design activities performed at IJCLAB included the FD-VD cryostat interface and installation aspects as well as thermal simulations (see Fig.16). Each 48 cards chimney is foreseen to be located at the vertex common to four CRP units and to then collect the signals from the corresponding four independent CRP quarters. This layout can be uniformly implemented on an infinite readout plane. Given the limited size of the detector, this 48 cards configuration is then common to the 63 chimneys placed at the centre of the cryostat. The 42 chimneys located at the detector periphery, due to a border effect in the connection to the CRPs, include only 24 cards needed for the readout of two CRP quarters and have therefore a smaller radius.

The FD-VD cryostat roof layout including the positions of the chimneys is shown in Fig.18.

Penetration Definition

Final conclusion : 2 types of chimneys for global optimization of the CRP cabling

- 63 penetrations on the center \varnothing 526 mm
- 42 penetrations on the sides \varnothing 381 mm

Fig. 18 Optimized penetrations layout foreseen for the 48 and 24 FE cards chimneys on the roof of FD-VD cryostat

The CAD models of the two kinds of chimneys are presented in Fig. 19. Both the 48 and 24 cards chimneys use the same warm-flanges for the cabling to the uTCA digitization electronics. The 48 cards model has two warm-flanges in a V-shape configuration. The 24 cards model hosts a single warm-flange. The open bottom views in the two cases in Fig. 19 allow seeing the position of the FE cards.

Fig.19 CAD models of the optimized 48 and 24 cards chimneys designed for FD-VD

Prototyping activities were launched in 2023, starting first with the 24 cards chimney, which has a more complicated and packed layout of the FE cards in order to fully exploit the available surface on the cold flange (see Fig. 20) and then for the 48 cards chimney.

Fig. 20 (Left) COMSOL thermal simulations for a 24 cards chimney (Right) warm flange for the large-size chimneys produced during the prototyping activities.

Since this integration aspect concerning the larger size chimneys could not be tested with the Cold-Box and NP02 cryostats, a dedicated integration setup was built and operated at EHN1 for the validation of the larger chimneys in 2024 (see Figure 21).

Fig. 21: Dedicated large-size chimney integration test performed in the Neutrino Platform EHN1 hall

3. CONCLUSIONS

The Vertical Drift design largely simplifies the construction and installation of giant liquid argon TPC detectors, given the fact that it replaces wire chambers with anodes made of layers of segmented printed circuit boards. The anode PCBs are assembled in independent modular elements (Charge Readout Planes) of about 3m size.

AIDAInnova contributed in supporting the developments on the Vertical Drift liquid argon Time Projection Chamber design for the readout of the top-drift volume of the DUNE FD-VD far detector module.

Fig. 22: Perspective view of the DUNE FD-VD far detector module

These developments included all the top-drift volume readout elements: the VD top-drift Charge Readout Planes, the associated readout electronics (TDE), optimized for the top-drift CRPs, and the signal feedthrough chimneys, providing access to the cryogenic analog electronics. All these elements proved to be well and stably performing during all the prototyping phase tests performed at the CERN Neutrino Platform.

All developments were successful in quickly reaching the maturity level needed for the construction of the DUNE Far Detector Module FD-VD (see Fig. 22). These aspects are described in more details in the DUNE Vertical Drift TDR [4]).

The production of the FD-VD detector elements and the associated readout electronics is currently in progress since 2024. In 2024 DUNE scheduled to install FD-VD as the first DUNE far detector module. The DUNE FD-VD technology forms as well the basis for the envisioned designs of the DUNE Phase II [5] Far Detector modules FD3 and FD4.

REFERENCES

- [1] NP02 Collaboration (2022) *Yearly progress report on NP02* CERN-SPSC-2022-014; SPSC-SR-308 (2022) <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2805710>
- [2] NP02 Collaboration (2023) *Yearly progress report on NP02* CERN-SPSC-2023-018 ; SPSC-SR-331 (2023) <http://cds.cern.ch/record/002857213>
- [3] NP02 Collaboration (2024) *Yearly progress report on* CERN-SPSC-2024-019 ; SPSC-SR-350 (2024) <http://cds.cern.ch/record/002896627#>
- [4] The DUNE Far Detector Vertical Drift Technology. Technical Design Report
DUNE Collaboration Adam Abed Abud (CERN) et al. (Dec 5, 2023)
Published in: JINST 19 (2024) 08, T08004 e-Print: 2312.03130 [hep-ex]
- [5] DUNE Phase II: scientific opportunities, detector concepts, technological solutions
DUNE Collaboration Adam Abed Abud (CERN) et al. (Aug 22, 2024)
Published in: JINST 19 (2024) 12, P12005 e-Print: 2408.12725 [physics.ins-det]

ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
AMC	Advanced Mezzanine Card (boards in uTCA form factor)
CB	Cold-Box cryostat/Time Projection Chamber
CRP	Charge Readout Plane (3x3.3m ² readout unit of Vertical Drift)
DUNE	Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment
FD-VD	First DUNE Far Detector module based on VD design (15 kton active LAr mass)
FE	Front-End
FDn n=1,..4	DUNE Far Detector Modules FD1,FD2,FD3,FD4
FR4	Flame Retardant 4 (PCB material)
LAr	Liquid Argon
MCH	MicroTCA Carrier Hub (uTCA crate controller)
NP02	Neutrino Platform Experiment 02
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
TDE	Top Drift Electronics
TPC	Time Projection Chamber
uTCA	MicroTCA
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
VD	Vertical Drift